

TOPSIM – Banking

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Keywords

Accounting, Asset management, Banking Management, Business, Controlling, Corporate Governance, Equity Management, Financial Management, Human Resource Management, Liquidity Management, Market Positioning, Risk Management, Strategic Decision-making

Figure 1. Overview of learning contents covered in TOPSIM – Banking. Graphic provided by TOPSIM (CC BY 4.0).

Introduction

TOPSIM – Banking (see Figure 1) is a sophisticated business simulation that conveys a comprehensive understanding of banking operations. Participants take on the role of the executive board of a medium-sized universal bank. The simulation covers business banking, wealth management, investment banking, and financial management. It prepares participants for challenges in the banking sector.

The simulation is suitable for bachelor's and master's programs in banking & finance as well as for the training and continuing education of branch and department managers, bank clerks, and (junior) executives.

As a serious game, TOPSIM – Banking creates a practice-oriented learning environment in which strategic and operational decisions are made, and economic interrelationships become tangible. Participants develop solid management competencies and are prepared for real professional challenges.

The game, played online via the TOPSIM cloud, provides a deep understanding of the challenges of bank management. Acting in leadership roles, participants make decisions across different business areas while competing with other teams in the market.

TOPSIM – Banking was first released in 2020 by TOPSIM GmbH and has been continuously developed since.

Facts

Release date:	Initial release: 2020, Current version: 2.0 (2024)
Developer:	TOPSIM GmbH
Game type:	Digital, hybrid (at least one player per team requires internet access)
Number of players:	Optimum: 9–25 (3–5 groups of 3–5 persons each) per market. Multiple markets are highly scalable infinitely scalable.
Format:	Asynchronous, Hybrid
Time frame:	Approx. 1–3 days, depending on the number of periods played, implementation method, and inclusion of evaluations or additional tasks. Time requirements depend on the intended learning outcomes.
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Device: Tablet, PC, or laptop with at least 720p resolution. Browser: Chrome, Firefox, or Safari. Internet access required.
Material:	Participants receive an introduction, a participant handbook, and additional seminar materials. Facilitators receive a seminar leader's handbook. Short description of the simulation: https://www.topsim.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/TOPSIM_%E2%80%93_Banking_Flyer.pdf Blog article: https://www.topsim.com/blog/banken-nachhaltig-zum-erfolg-fuehren-mit-topsim-banking/
Price:	TOPSIM simulations are fee-based. Exact costs depend on the specific simulation, number of participants, and usage model. Simulations are provided digitally. For precise pricing, a direct inquiry with TOPSIM is recommended, as costs are calculated individually.

Resonance & Criticism

TOPSIM – Banking has been positively received by participants and professionals. Participants praise the practical teaching of bank management while adhering to current regulatory requirements (Hochschule Trier – Trier University of Applied Sciences, 2018).

TOPSIM – Banking has not received awards. Some participants criticize the simulation's complexity, as it can be challenging. However, the simulation allows adjustments to difficulty levels to match different knowledge levels.

Game Principle & Process

TOPSIM – Banking is based on a realistic simulation of bank management. Participants assume leadership roles and make strategic and operational decisions. They must analyze market conditions, meet regulatory requirements, and ensure the long-term competitiveness of their bank. Up to five periods (financial years), each with up to 67 decisions, can be played, all of which directly influence gameplay.

The goal is to lead the bank to sustainable success. This includes maximizing profitability, ensuring liquidity, and meeting regulatory requirements. Clear KPIs—customer satisfaction, service quality, and brand index—help participants measure progress.

The simulation provides continuous feedback through financial indicators, market developments, and customer reactions. Decisions have immediate effects on company performance. Through data analysis, participants learn to adjust their strategies to achieve long-term success.

Participants compete in teams for market share. This fosters communication, collaboration, and strategic thinking. Team discussions and negotiations simulate real-world management challenges.

The game is based on business and financial models, including portfolio theory, risk-management strategies, and banking management instruments. It also incorporates principles of corporate management, market analysis, and strategic planning.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

TOPSIM – Banking conveys a comprehensive understanding of banking operations and supports participants in achieving core learning and training goals. A key focus lies in recognizing company-wide interdependencies: participants understand the interactions between business areas and their influence on overall bank performance. They also learn to analyze market situations using controlling tools to make well-founded decisions.

Another objective is conducting strategic analyses. Participants develop competitive strategies for products, markets, and target groups and implement them purposefully. Analyzing bank-specific metrics—especially financial indicators for assessing bank stability—plays a central role. Participants also engage with various financing strategies, comparing equity and debt financing options while considering regulatory requirements.

The simulation realistically reflects banking operations. Participants make strategic and operational decisions across business banking, wealth management, and investment banking. Direct feedback on decisions enables hands-on learning. Current regulatory requirements are integrated to demonstrate their effects on bank management.

Facilitators act as moderators and guides. They introduce game mechanics, supervise processes, assist with questions, and lead reflection phases where decisions are analyzed. For groups of three to five teams, each with three to five participants, one instructor is sufficient. The simulation of a competitive market requires well-founded decisions and analysis. Realistic market conditions and regulatory requirements create a practice-oriented learning environment that prepares participants for challenges in the banking sector.

Effectiveness

Empirical studies on the effectiveness of TOPSIM – Banking are limited. A report from Hochschule Trier indicates that participants developed a deeper understanding of bank management through the simulation, particularly regarding profitability, liquidity, and regulatory requirements (Hochschule Trier – Trier University of Applied Sciences, 2018).

While empirical data on long-term learning effects and immersive user experience are limited, realistic simulations of company-wide interdependencies and the direct application of control instruments promote active engagement with banking decisions. The combination of competition, decision pressure, and direct feedback may contribute to a flow state in which skills and challenges are balanced. Studies specifically measuring this effect within TOPSIM – Banking do not yet exist.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

TOPSIM – Banking does not include sensitive topics. The simulation focuses on economic decisions and bank management without using discriminatory content or stereotypes.

The simulation is based on fundamental economic mechanisms and is updated regularly to reflect regulatory and market changes. Accessibility may be challenging for individuals with visual impairments or motor limitations due to the game's reliance on complex tables and analyses.

Ethical considerations, such as banks' social responsibility, are not explicitly addressed. Facilitators may find it beneficial to encourage discussions on the societal impacts of decisions made within the game.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Hannes Hamester

Sources

Hochschule Trier. (2018, January 25). Erfahrungsbericht Seminar TOPSIM - Universal Banking. <https://www.hochschule-trier.de/hochschule/organisation/qm/qm-aktuelles/beitrag-ausfuehrlich/erfahrungsbericht-seminar-topsim-universal-banking>

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